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#STI2022GRX

Full paper

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Contribution Score: Crediting contributions among co-authors

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Introduction

Co-authorship practices vary across fields, within fields, and within the oeuvre of individual scientists. To deal with such variations, science-based scientometrics traditionally uses fractional counting of the contributions of researchers, institutions, and countries to compare co-authored publications and their received citations. Fractional counting is preferred for field normalization (Waltman & van Eck, 2015), and it allows the sum of the contributions of all units to be equal to the actual output in the system while avoiding an inflated perception of the actual output of a unit (Sugimoto & Larivière, 2018).

Full counting (each co-author is credited one publication) flourishes outside of science-based scientometrics, even in professional information sources such as ORCID or the Author Profiles in Scopus. An analysis of Clarivate’s Annual Highly Cited Researchers List showed that researchers with the highest total citation counts more often than others take part in large teams in research (Aksnes & Aagaard, 2021). Full counting is particularly widespread in in daily-life practices: Any search for an author name in a bibliographic data source will return a certain number of publications. This number is often transferred directly to contexts of research assessment and presented in, e.g., CVs and annual reports. The total number of citations is often added in the same way. Such easy practices will probably prevail even in an era with increased attention to responsible metrics and the principles of justice, equity, diversity, and inclusion in qualitative research assessment.

Our project addresses the problem of how to fairly represent contributions to collaborative research projects in all contexts where they are summed up by numbers. The aim the project is

to develop a tool named Contribution Score as fair and practical for crediting contributions among co-authors in the contexts described above. We present and discuss the results from the first phase of the project in this paper.

In this first phase, we conducted a global survey among active researchers publishing in all areas of research. The respondents were asked how and to what extent they had contributed to collaborative research projects that were successfully published in three recently published original research articles where they appeared as co-authors. The selected three articles for each respondent represented different teams and numbers of authors.

The purpose of the survey was to gain new knowledge about contributions to collaborative projects and to validate how the contributions of co-authors are represented by bibliometric counting methods. Our results show that neither of the two methods mentioned above, full and fractional counting, are representative for self-reported contributions to collaborative projects. The intermediate counting method presented as Modified Fractional Counting (MFC) in (Sivertsen et al., 2019) comes much closer to simulating what the respondents consider their relative contribution. An aim in this phase of the project is to validate the MFC as a possible counting method at the level of individual researchers and thereby to take a first step towards developing the Contribution Score.

The MFC applies the square root of the fraction instead of the fraction. It was introduced in 2019 as the result of a bibliometric analysis of more than 44,000 publications during seven years by 4,000 identifiable active individual researchers with comparable resources to perform research. The study found that neither full nor fractional counting make contributions comparable across different co-authorship practices. Full counting overestimates them while fractional counting underestimates them. The MFC was demonstrated to balance between the different co-authorship practices that may exist among authors even within the same field of research. By applying MFC, it was also shown that scientists in different areas of research have comparable average contributions to scientific articles. Sivertsen et al. (2019) argued that, compared to traditional fractional counting, MFC reflects the overlapping of responsibilities in team research which also follow from publication ethics.

The study presented here is also inspired by the successful implementation of CRediT statements in an increasing number of journals (casrai.org/credit). This practice confirms that co-authors perform overlapping tasks in the research they report in a publication. We designed our survey to not only reflect the degree of the contribution, but also to reflect how specific tasks were shared between the respondents and their co-authors in each article.

The MFC was developed for aggregated analysis of the contributions of institutions and countries. Taking it down to the level of individual researchers as a solution for the Contribution Score has several challenges. We will discuss them after presenting the survey and its results.

Data and methods

We used Scopus data to prepare the survey and collect other information about the respondents. Scopus is a source-neutral abstract and citation database with more than 84 million publication records and 17.6 million author profiles. We selected 49,455 authors worldwide in all areas of research from Scopus by applying four filters:

- 1) Active with at least one publication each year 2016-2020
- 2) At least one publication with a CRediT statement recorded in 2020 or 2021

- 3) Variations in the numbers and names of co-authors among their publications
- 4) A recorded email address

The second criterium was introduced because we wanted the respondents to be familiar with classifications of author roles. In a later phase of this project, we will also be able to compare the responses in the survey to the declared credit statements in the publication. We enriched the Scopus data with ScienceDirect full-text APIs to extract the CRediT information.

To measure the variation for the third criterium, we calculated the Gini index based on the list of number of co-authors across the researcher's career length publications. The Gini index is a measure of statistical dispersion which originally was developed for measuring economic inequality. The value of the Gini index ranges from 0 to 1, with 1 being perfectly unequal, and 0 being perfectly equal. With our application, a Gini index close to 1 would represent a dramatic change of co-authorship practices within a career, while a Gini index close to 0 would represent very stable practices. We selected researchers with an index in the range of 0.3 to 0.7 which ensures a combination of stability and dynamics in the size of the teams a researcher has been engaged in.

With the application of the four criteria, the screening process resulted in 49,455 target respondents for the survey. They were contacted by email with a cover letter (see Appendix 1) addressing them individually. The cover letter provided them with a list of their three selected publications and a link to the online survey (Appendix 2).

The three publications that we asked each respondent about in this survey were selected through the following screening steps:

- 1) Potential respondents with less than three publications (research articles or reviews) with a minimum of two authors were excluded. Among the others, we selected the most recent publications, up to ten if they had more than ten.
- 2) From the resulting selection, we identified the most recent publication for each potential respondent as publication 1.
- 3) Publication 2 was selected as the one with the fewest co-authors in common with publication 1 because we wanted diversity. If this criterium provided more than one publication to choose from, we added recency as a second criterium.
- 4) Publication 3 was selected by a similar approach, but in cases of more than one alternative, we selected the publication with the largest Euclidean distance to publication 1 and 2 regarding common co-authors. Again, the intention was to ensure that the respondents reported from work in different teams.

To keep the survey short, we only asked two additional demographic questions about gender and career stage. Other information such as country of the affiliation, research area, career length, and citation impact could be derived from Scopus database.

Analysis of possible biases in the survey results

With valid responses from 2,812 respondents, the response rate was 5.7%. To check possible bias, we compare them all to non-respondents in the original target group regarding gender, geographic location, research area, career age, citation impact, and h-index. For non-

respondents, gender was inferred from NamSor data. Our group of respondents proved to be unbiased on this background (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Comparison of the 2,812 respondents and 46,643 non-respondents of the survey across career age, citation count, h-index, region, research domain and gender, based on percentile and percentage distribution.

The results of the two demographic questions in the survey showed that we had a higher proportion of men among the respondents than women (Table 1), and that the respondents tended to be established researchers (Table 2). By asking about gender (Table 1), we were able to identify any gender bias among the respondents. As shown in Figure 1, the proportions among the respondents reasonably reflected the proportions within the target cohort. Later in this project, we will do a follow up study to see if there are gender differences in reported contributions to publications.

Table 1. Survey results: Distribution of respondents by gender

Gender	Number of respondents
Male	1914
Female	830
Transgender	1
Non-binary	4
Prefer not to say	49
Skipped this question	14

Most respondents were established researchers (Table 2). This is as expected regarding the filters we applied to determine the target cohort.

Table 2. Survey results: Distribution of respondents by career stage

Career stage	Number of respondents
Established researcher	2213
Early career researcher	495
Student	85
Other	19

We checked the consistency of answers by looking closely at 177 publications that more than one respondent had reported their contribution to. These publications represented a cohort of 346 respondents. Most of the 177 publications had two respondents as co-authors (Table 3). We checked the respondents' answers about their types of contributions (see Appendix 2, the STI 2022 | <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6951780>)

second question on page two of the survey). Where two or more respondents answered that they were the only contributor of a specific role in the same publication, we considered this as a 'contradictory answer'. We then counted the number of publications which contained such contradictory answers for each of the roles (Table 4).

Table 3. Distribution of publications count based on number of respondents asked for the same publication:

<i>Number of respondents asked for the same publication</i>	<i>Number of publications</i>
2	155
3	17
4	3
5	2

Table 4. Number of publications in question for each role which had contradictory answers from respondents:

<i>Role</i>	<i>Number of publications which contained contradictory answers</i>	<i>Contradictory rate (Number of publications which contained contradictory answers/total number of publications had multiple respondents)</i>
<i>Conceptualization</i>	4	2.3%
<i>Methodology</i>	6	3.4%
<i>Investigation</i>	6	3.4%
<i>Data curation</i>	7	4.0%
<i>Formal analysis and validation</i>	4	2.3%
<i>Writing-original draft</i>	6	3.4%
<i>Writing-review and editing</i>	17	9.6%
<i>Project administration and supervision</i>	4	2.3%

The results demonstrate some contradicting responses, which is as expected in a survey asking for perceived activities in the past. The role of 'Writing - review and editing' has a clearly higher contradictory rate which might reflect that this is often the responsibility of more than one author. In our survey, 77 percent of the respondents claimed that the whole team contributed to this task in at least one of their publications.

Main result of the survey: validation of MFC

The main aim in this phase of the project was to validate the MFC as a possible method for Contribution Score at the level of individual researchers. Figure 2 shows the main result from the survey that is related to the validation.

Figure 2. Self-reported contributions to 8,346 specific publications with different numbers of authors, as reported by 2,812 contributing authors on the scale of 0-100 and rescaled to 0-1 here, compared to full counting, fractional counting and modified fractional counting (Contribution Score) of the same publications.

The respondents were asked for the extent of their contribution to the work on a scale of 0-100. The relative contribution is compared to the number of authors involved in the publication (the diagram to the right). We observe that the relative contribution of an author decreases with the total number authors in the publication. It is a sign of division of labour. The efforts of one author decreases when more authors are involved. However, our survey also shows that tasks overlap between the respondent and the other authors. We do not know whether shared tasks also imply overlapping responsibilities for each other's contributions. We only know that research and publication ethics demand shared responsibility for the whole work.

We do observe, however, that Modified Fractional Counting as used in Sivertsen et al., (2019) comes closest to simulating the self-reported extent of contributions. The finding in Figure 2 is thereby a validation of MFC as preferable to traditional fractional counting and full counting.

Our closer analysis of this main result showed that MFC agrees with self-reported scores across different fields of research and especially well for the most common co-authorship group sizes (up to 8-9 co-authors). We found an even better agreement between MFC and self-reported contributions when excluding 998 (12 percent) publications in which the respondent was first author. First authors contribute relatively more to publications in all sizes of teams.

Discussion

We have reported the results from the first phase of a project aimed to introduce a tool named Contribution Score (CS) to the daily-life contexts where publications and citations at the level of individual researchers are listed and/or counted. Our results so far imply that Modified Fractional Counting (MFC) might be preferable to traditional fractional counting and full counting. In contexts where full counting is practiced, we intend to suggest CS as a supplement. Our results indicate that the number of publications as first author (and perhaps also corresponding author) should be presented in addition to CS.

In our further work, we will face several challenges when developing and implementing CS as a useful and legitimate tool. A major task in the development phase is to solve possible questions and issues arising from the state of art in the scientific field of scientometrics. This is

our reason for presenting results from the first phase at STI 2022. Our discussion below will address such possible issues.

Traditional fractional counting is considered to lead to a more proper field normalization (Waltman & van Eck, 2015). This is not an argument against MFC. It was shown by Sivertsen et al. (2019) that MFC performs better than traditional fractional counting by balancing between fields and among different co-authorship practices within the same field. Two other studies have demonstrated paradoxes in how traditional fractional counting works. Gasson et al. (2019) showed that the productivity of scientists as measured by fractional counting goes down as collaboration and team sizes increase. Demaine (2022) recently demonstrated that the (fractionalized) aggregated citation impact of universities decreases as collaboration between them increases.

A more challenging possible argument against CS is that the contribution of all co-authors will add up to more than one publication. According to Sugimoto & Larivière (2018), “the advantage of fractional counting is that the sum of articles of all units in the system is equal to the actual output in the system.” This argument is valid if publications are viewed as contributions to the scientific *literature* (the information science perspective). However, according to the purposes of most bibliometric analysis, publications are viewed as representations of the *scientific work* that is reported in the publications. A social science perspective is then needed with a critical investigation of appropriate methods from the perspective of real-world representation. Our results indicate that traditional fractional counting underestimates the efforts of individual contributing to team science. A social scientist would then say the method needs to be tested and improved. From this perspective, MFC is preferable even if the contributions to one publication add up to more than one when aggregated. MFC reflects that the responsibilities overlap in the teamwork that leads to a co-authored publication.

Another challenging argument against CS is normative: An indicator should not incentivize the trend towards increasing number of authors per article. In a study with a similar starting point as ours, observations based on CRediT statements by co-authors, Larivière et al. (2021) conclude that such statements express and reinforce trends toward seeking to create credits for accountability and competition rather than new knowledge among researchers. The trends are worrying from the perspective of research evaluation, science policy, and responsible research practices. From this perspective, CS can be viewed as a damage. We share the same worries but cannot see that traditional fractional counting solves the problem either. Fractional counting is seldom practiced beyond science-based scientometrics. A reason might be that it is perceived among researchers as not representing teamwork properly. If full counting remains the widespread practice, the trend towards crediting more authors will certainly continue.

In our view, the major challenges with legitimacy arise as we take the step down from the aggregate level that the MFC was designed for to the individual level that we are developing the CS for. At the aggregate level, with the Leiden Ranking of Universities as an example, the order and roles of authors are usually not considered. It is probably unnecessary. Sivertsen et al. (2019) tested the harmonic counting method suggested by Hagen (2008), which is a variant of fractional counting that considers the sequence of authors. It made very little difference at the aggregate level of universities. We know, however, that author order makes much difference at the individual level, but perhaps not in the immediate aggregations of publications and citations per author that the CS is intended for? So far, we intend to avoid the problems with applying measurements based on author order across fields with different traditions and premises for assigning such sequences. We think a supplementary count of articles as first

author (and perhaps corresponding author) might be more practical and easier to establish from a list of publications. Anyways, we need to deal even more carefully with such questions as we apply CS to citations.

The perhaps greatest challenge was mentioned in the introduction: To suggest a new bibliometric indicator at the individual level in an era with increased attention to responsible metrics and qualitative research assessment based on the principles of justice, equity, diversity, and inclusion. We will have to argue that CS is preferable if full counting cannot be totally extinguished from bibliographic information systems and research assessment practices. Then, we can argue that the CS is:

- Simple: Easy to understand, no complex algorithms
- Unbiased: Stable across fields and co-authorship practices
- Complementary: Useful complement to full or fractional counting
- Validated: Comparable with self-reported contributions
- Adopted: Already in use for national purposes to measure institutional contributions in Norway

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Appendix 1-The invitation email for the survey

Dear Dr. Gunnar Sivertsen,

Our research group is performing a study in collaboration with the [International Center for the Study of Research \(ICSR\)](#) in which we are exploring different approaches to understanding the individual contributions of researchers who work in teams.

To aid our research, we invite you to take part in a survey about your contributions to three of your recent research publications. We expect the survey to take approximately 6 minutes of your time.

Please click on the link below to participate in the survey:

[Start survey](#)

Our research seeks to address inconsistencies in the way that research productivity is measured through authorship of research publications. A previous study from ICSR, [Fractional Authorship & Publication Productivity](#), found that researchers' productivity decreases with increasing teamwork when a typical counting method is used: that is, where publication credit is divided equally amongst the publication's authors. The recent introduction of the [CRedit \(Contributor Roles Taxonomy\)](#) in scientific journals, clearly demonstrates that co-authors overlap in their tasks, and the [ICMJE guidelines for authorship](#) demand collective responsibility for the whole work.

In completing the survey, you will be contributing to the development of publication-based indicators that more fairly and comprehensively reflect researcher productivity. We aim to publish the results of this study in one or more peer-reviewed publications in a timely manner.

Your responses will remain completely confidential. You will not be identified or contacted unless you specifically request to be. If you have any questions about this survey, please email our research group at a.ding@elsevier.com.

Best regards,

Gunnar Sivertsen*, Research Professor, Nordic Institute for Studies in Innovation, Research and Education, Oslo, Norway,
Lin Zhang*, Professor, School of Information Management, Wuhan University, China, and Guest professor, KU Leuven, Belgium,
Andrew Plume*, Director, ICSR, Oxford, United Kingdom,
Alvin Ding, Research Evaluation Manager, ICSR, Beijing, China.

* Member of the ICSR Advisory Board (<https://www.elsevier.com/icsr/advisory-board>).

Appendix 2-Screenshots of the survey questions

We found the three publications below in Scopus. Do you recognize them as an author?

Yes, the publication details are correct

No, some or all of the publication details are incorrect

We will ask about the following recent publication(s) in which you are listed as an author.

Please indicate below if these publication details are correct.

Publication 1
"Petr M., Engels T.C.E., Kulczycki E., Dušková M., Guns R., Sieberová M., Sivertsen G."
Journal article publishing in the social sciences and humanities: A comparison of Web of Science coverage for five European countries
PLoS ONE
2021

Publication 2
"Sivertsen G., Meijer I."
"Normal versus extraordinary societal impact: How to understand, evaluate, and improve research activities in their relations to society?"
Research Evaluation
2020

Publication 3
"Zhang L., Zhao W., Liu J., Sivertsen G., Huang Y."
Do national funding organizations properly address the diseases with the highest burden?: Observations from China and the UK
Scientometrics
2020

>>

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Thinking about your work recently published as:

"Petr M., Engels T.C.E., Kulczycki E., Dušková M., Guns R., Sieberová M., Sivertsen G."
Journal article publishing in the social sciences and humanities: A comparison of Web of Science coverage for five European countries
PLoS ONE
2021

On a scale from 0 to 100, to what degree were you involved in the total work leading to this publication?

Use the slider below to indicate your contribution.

0

100

Who was involved in which tasks?

Select both 'Me' and 'Other authors' if tasks were shared.

	Me	Other authors	Task not relevant to this publication
Conceptualization	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Methodology	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Investigation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data curation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Formal analysis and validation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Writing – original draft	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Writing – review & editing	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Project administration and supervision	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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